

6G SNS

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D4.4 – FEDERATED AI/ML

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Definition
6G	Sixth Generation
AC	Anonymous Credential
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMD	Advanced Micro Devices
ARM	Advanced RISC Machines
BFL	Blockchain-based Federated Learning
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DID	Decentralized Identifiers
DLG	Deep Leakage from Gradients
DP	Differential Privacy
EU	European Union
FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
FL	Federated Learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IID	Independent and Identically Distributed
IoT	Internet of Things
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON for Linked Data
LDP	Local Differential Privacy
ML	Machine Learning
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PBFT	Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance
PFL	Personalized Federated Learning
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PoF	Proof-of-Federation
PS	Parameter-Server
RAN	Radio Access Network
RATS	Remote Attestation Procedures

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RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
SEV-SNP	Secure Encrypted Virtualization – Secure Nested Paging
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
TDX	Trust Domain Extensions
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
VC	Verifiable Credentials
VM	Virtual Machine
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package
ZKP	Zero-Knowledge Proof

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable (D4.4 – Federated AI/ML) defines the architecture, requirements, and enabling technologies for secure and privacy-preserving federated learning within the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. The document specifies how federated AI/ML can be safely deployed across heterogeneous 6G cloud–edge environments, allowing collaborative model training while ensuring that sensitive data remains local and protected throughout the learning lifecycle.

The deliverable consolidates background and state-of-the-art insights on federated learning in 6G, identifies key security, privacy, and trust challenges, and derives a set of functional, security, governance, and operational requirements that guide system design. It then presents the overall federated AI/ML architecture developed under this task, which brings together confidential orchestration, federated learning coordination, cryptographic trust mechanisms, and secure execution across cloud-edge environments. The architecture builds on the confidential orchestration foundations established in Deliverable 4.3 and integrates key enablers from WP2—such as Decentralized Identifiers, Verifiable Credentials, and Zero-Knowledge Proofs—to support verifiable, policy-driven, and privacy-preserving participation throughout the federated learning lifecycle.

Within this architecture, blockchain-enabled aggregation is introduced as a complementary mechanism to strengthen integrity, auditability, and decentralized trust in model management and aggregation workflows by removing single points of failure and providing tamper-evident provenance for AI/ML models. In parallel, the deliverable reports algorithmic contributions that enhance robustness and fairness under non-IID data distributions and device heterogeneity, ensuring that the proposed architecture remains effective under realistic deployment conditions.

Finally, the document outlines how the Federated AI/ML integrates with WP5 use cases, demonstrating its relevance for real-world validation scenarios. Overall, this deliverable establishes a coherent and secure federated learning foundation that supports CONFIDENTIAL6G’s objectives for trustworthy, privacy-preserving AI in next-generation 6G environments.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 SCOPE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This final report (D4.4, *Federated AI/ML*) specifies the CONFIDENTIAL6G federated AI/ML system for 6G-era confidential networking and multi-party data spaces. It describes the target architecture, security and privacy requirements, and the technology enablers needed to support federated learning across the cloud–edge continuum while keeping data local, protecting model updates, and enabling verifiable collaboration across administrative domains. In addition, it summarizes the selected methods and mechanisms—covering confidential orchestration, privacy-enhancing techniques, and decentralized trust components—and reports the current status of implementation and integration towards WP5 use-case validation.

1.2 DOCUMENT ORGANIZATION

The remainder of this document is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews background and state-of-the-art for federated learning in 6G, including key security/privacy risks and relevant cryptographic and trust enablers. Section 3 consolidates the functional, security, privacy, and telecom-driven requirements that guide the system design. Section 4 presents the proposed architecture and technology enablers, including confidential orchestration, identity and trust layers, and secure aggregation approaches, and links them to integration aspects in the project. Section 5 outlines the roadmap towards full integration and evaluation. Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

2 BACKGROUND AND STATE-OF-THE-ART

2.1 FEDERATED LEARNING IN 6G NETWORKS AND ITS RELEVANCE TO O-RAN

The evolution toward Sixth Generation (6G) networks marks a paradigm shift from connectivity-centric architectures to intelligence-driven systems. Future 6G infrastructures will integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) capabilities natively across all network layers to enable self-organizing, context-aware, and energy-efficient operations.

Within this vision, Federated Learning (FL) has emerged as a core enabler for distributed and privacy-preserving AI. Instead of transferring raw data to a centralized server, FL allows multiple nodes—such as edge devices, base stations, or cloud servers—to train local models collaboratively and exchange only model parameters or gradients. This decentralization reduces communication overhead, protects user privacy, and supports localized adaptation, which are key requirements for large-scale 6G deployments.

In 6G environments, where vast amounts of heterogeneous data are generated at the edge, FL provides a scalable way to exploit such data without violating confidentiality regulations. It enables intelligence at the edge, allowing the network to react dynamically to radio conditions, user mobility, and application demands. The 6G vision also emphasizes trust, security, and sustainability, making FL particularly attractive when combined with mechanisms such as Differential Privacy (DP), Homomorphic Encryption (HE), Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), and Fairness—all of which are explored in this task.

While Task 4.4 focuses on developing a secure and privacy-preserving FL orchestration framework, the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture provides a realistic and representative deployment context. O-RAN introduces open interfaces and disaggregated components (e.g., Near-Real-Time and Non-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs)) that enable intelligent control of radio resources. These distributed RICs can act as federated clients, collaboratively training models based on localized network data while adhering to operator and privacy constraints. Therefore, O-RAN serves as an applicability domain where the proposed FL mechanisms can be validated under real-world conditions involving multiple base stations, diverse datasets, and dynamic network topologies.

Deploying FL within 6G and O-RAN ecosystems, however, introduces several technical challenges. These include heterogeneous hardware and software capabilities, varying data distributions (non-IID data), intermittent connectivity between nodes, and strict latency requirements for model aggregation. Moreover, the limited computational and energy resources available at the edge demand efficient orchestration, adaptive resource allocation,

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and secure model exchange mechanisms. Addressing these challenges requires seamless integration with confidential orchestration frameworks (Task 4.3), cryptographic enablers (WP2), and AI/ML methods (WP3)—all converging within the architectural design presented in this deliverable.

In summary, FL represents a fundamental building block for realizing distributed, trustworthy, and intelligent 6G networks. Although O-RAN is not the primary focus of Task 4.4, it provides an essential reference environment for demonstrating how privacy-preserving FL, secure orchestration, and cryptographic mechanisms can enhance the reliability and trustworthiness of future 6G systems.

2.2 SECURITY AND PRIVACY RISKS IN FEDERATED LEARNING

While FL provides an effective framework for privacy-preserving distributed intelligence, it also introduces new security and privacy vulnerabilities that must be carefully addressed before real-world deployment in 6G environments. The distributed and semi-trusted nature of FL—where model training occurs across heterogeneous and potentially adversarial nodes—creates multiple attack surfaces that can compromise confidentiality, integrity, and fairness of the global model.

2.2.1 DATA AND MODEL HETEROGENEITY (NON-IID CHALLENGES)

A major characteristic of real-world FL deployments is the non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) nature of local data. In 6G and O-RAN networks, each edge node or base station observes a unique subset of user or traffic data that may differ significantly in scale, distribution, or context. This heterogeneity can degrade convergence, bias the global model, and cause inconsistent behaviour across nodes.

From a security perspective, non-IID data makes anomaly detection more difficult—since malicious updates may appear statistically legitimate within a local context—and thus complicates the identification of adversarial participants. Furthermore, uneven data quality or quantity can lead to fairness issues, where certain nodes or user groups dominate the learning outcome, undermining trust and transparency.

2.2.2 DATA POISONING AND MODEL POISONING ATTACKS

In data poisoning, adversaries intentionally modify their local training datasets (e.g., inserting mislabelled or adversarial samples) to corrupt the resulting model. In model poisoning, attackers manipulate their gradient or weight updates before submission, biasing the aggregation process to achieve a malicious objective. Such attacks can severely disrupt intelligent network functions in 6G—for example, steering a resource-allocation model toward sub-optimal configurations or degrading Quality of Service (QoS). Because FL typically aggregates updates in encrypted or privacy-preserving form, detecting poisoned

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contributions is non-trivial. This calls for robust aggregation mechanisms and trust-based participant evaluation, which are key elements explored later in Task 4.4.

2.2.3 INFERENCE AND GRADIENT LEAKAGE

Even when raw data remains local, gradient updates can inadvertently leak sensitive information. Research such as *Deep Leakage from Gradients (DLG)* has shown that an attacker observing only gradients can reconstruct aspects of the original training data. In the 6G context, such leakage could expose users' location traces, traffic profiles, or device-specific information. This risk highlights the necessity for privacy-preserving cryptographic techniques, including Differential Privacy (DP), Homomorphic Encryption (HE), and Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), which are directly integrated as enablers in Task 4.4.

2.2.4 BACKDOOR AND FREE-RIDER ATTACKS

Backdoor attacks embed hidden triggers into the model so that specific inputs yield attacker-chosen outputs at inference time. These attacks are particularly insidious in large-scale collaborative systems, as they may remain dormant until specific conditions are met. Free-rider attacks occur when a participant uploads fabricated or low-quality updates to gain access to the aggregated global model without performing legitimate training. Both types of behaviour undermine the integrity and trustworthiness of the FL ecosystem and necessitate mechanisms for participant reputation tracking, attestation, and decentralized auditability, which are core objectives of the blockchain layer in Task 4.4.

2.3 CRYPTOGRAPHIC ENABLERS (DP, HE, SMPC, DIDS)

This section introduces the cryptographic enablers developed in WP2 and explains their role in enabling secure, confidential and privacy-preserving Federated AI/ML (FL) under Task 4.4. Federated Learning in 6G involves multiple data owners collaboratively training models without sharing raw data; therefore, strong confidentiality, verifiability, and identity security mechanisms are required to ensure trustworthy model updates, prevent information leakage, and protect data sovereignty.

2.3.1 CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND CONFIDENTIAL VIRTUAL MACHINES (CVMS)

Confidential Computing provides hardware-protected execution environments that isolate code and data even from privileged system software, using technologies such as AMD SEV-SNP [1], Intel TDX [2], and Arm CCA [3]. These confidential VMs ensure that memory remains encrypted and attested, which prevents adversaries—including cloud administrators—from accessing FL clients' gradients, intermediate states, or local training data. In Task 4.4, CVMs form the trusted execution base for deploying federated learning components across edge

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and cloud infrastructures, enabling confidential orchestration from Task 4.3 while guaranteeing that model updates remain protected during computation and communication.

2.3.2 DIFFERENTIAL PRIVACY (DP)

Differential Privacy provides mathematically provable privacy guarantees by adding calibrated noise to model gradients or updates, ensuring that the presence or absence of any individual data record cannot be inferred [4], and implemented in practice through DP-SGD [5]. In the context of Task 4.4, DP prevents sensitive information from leaking through gradient updates during federated learning rounds, mitigating attacks such as membership inference and gradient inversion. This makes DP a core layer of defence for safeguarding personal and domain-sensitive datasets while enabling collaborative AI/ML across distributed 6G data spaces.

2.3.3 HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION (HE)

Homomorphic Encryption enables computation on encrypted data without requiring decryption, using schemes such as BFV [6], BGV [7], FV [8] for exact arithmetic, CKKS for approximate ML-compatible arithmetic [9], and TFHE for efficient Boolean operations [10]. This capability is critical for federated learning in Task 4.4 because encrypted gradients from different clients can be aggregated by the server without exposing any underlying values. HE therefore ensures that even a curious or semi-trusted aggregator cannot access private training information, supporting data sovereignty and cross-domain confidentiality requirements in 6G FL deployments.

2.3.4 SECURE MULTI-PARTY COMPUTATION (SMPC)

Secure Multi-Party Computation allows multiple parties to jointly compute a function while keeping their inputs private, using foundational mechanisms such as Shamir secret sharing [11] and widely used protocols like SPDZ [12]. Within Task 4.4, SMPC enables privacy-preserving secure aggregation of client updates in settings where no single entity is fully trusted, ensuring that the aggregated model is correct while preventing any party from learning another client's gradients. This makes SMPC an essential enabler for federated learning across mutually distrustful domains, as expected in WP5's multi-stakeholder 6G scenarios.

2.3.5 THRESHOLD CRYPTOGRAPHY AND DISTRIBUTED KEY GENERATION (DKG)

Threshold cryptography distributes cryptographic secrets among multiple parties so that only a threshold of participants can perform operations such as decryption or signing, with classical schemes including Feldman VSS [13], Pedersen VSS [14], and later publicly verifiable PVSS constructions [15], as well as recent post-quantum variants [16]. For Task 4.4, threshold cryptography ensures that homomorphically aggregated ML updates can only

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be decrypted when sufficient authorized participants collaborate, preventing any single party, including the aggregator, from unilaterally accessing plaintext model parameters. This enhances decentralization and resilience in the federated learning workflow and aligns with Confidential6G's distributed trust model.

2.3.6 MULTI-KEY HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION (MK-HE)

Multi-Key HE extends traditional HE by allowing ciphertexts encrypted under different client keys to be jointly evaluated, as introduced in early MK-FHE schemes by Mukherjee and Wichs [17] and refined in CKKS-based MK-HE implementations [18]. This is particularly important for Task 4.4 because each FL participant may use its own encryption key, preserving full data sovereignty while still enabling the server to perform encrypted operations across heterogeneous ciphertexts. MK-HE therefore allows multi-domain federated learning without key-sharing requirements, supporting privacy-preserving collaboration among stakeholders in WP5 use cases.

2.3.7 DECENTRALIZED IDENTIFIERS (DIDS) AND VERIFIABLE CREDENTIALS (VCS)

Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), as standardized by the W3C DID Core specification [19], provide self-sovereign, cryptographically verifiable identities that do not depend on central authorities, while Verifiable Credentials [20] allow issuing and validating tamper-proof claims. Task 4.4 uses DIDs to authenticate FL participants in a privacy-preserving manner, enabling them to prove eligibility and trustworthiness without revealing their real-world identity. DIDs also bind cryptographic keys such as HE or SMPC shares to verifiable identities, strengthening access control and participant lifecycle management across federated training rounds.

2.3.8 ZERO-KNOWLEDGE PROOFS (ZKPS)

Zero-Knowledge Proofs allow one party to prove that a statement is true without revealing any underlying information, building on foundational work by Goldwasser, Micali, and Rackoff [21] and practical systems such as ZK-SNARKs [22] and Bulletproofs [23]. In Task 4.4, ZKPs enable clients to prove that they executed local training correctly, adhered to DP noise requirements, or used valid gradient dimensions without leaking training data or model internals. This strengthens the trustworthiness of federated learning by preventing malicious behaviour and ensuring verifiable correctness across confidential data spaces.

2.3.9 POST-QUANTUM CRYPTOGRAPHY (PQC)

Post-Quantum Cryptography provides security against quantum adversaries using lattice-based, hash-based, and code-based cryptographic primitives, with NIST standardizing

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schemes such as Kyber (KEM) and Dilithium (signature) [24]. Since 6G systems will operate in a post-quantum threat landscape, Task 4.4 integrates PQC to protect federated learning keys, secure encryption channels, and model provenance records from long-term quantum attacks. PQC ensures that confidential training data and model updates remain secure throughout the lifecycle of the federated learning process.

2.4 BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FL AGGREGATION

Traditional FL relies on a central aggregator that collects model updates from distributed clients and fuses them into a global model. While effective in many cases, this centralized approach introduces significant limitations—most notably a single point of failure, vulnerability to malicious or biased aggregators, and the lack of transparent accountability for how model updates are combined. As FL systems move toward large-scale, multi-stakeholder 6G and edge environments, these weaknesses become even more pronounced.

To overcome these issues, researchers have turned to blockchain-based Federated Learning (BFL) frameworks that merge the strengths of distributed ledger technology with collaborative machine learning. In such designs, blockchain acts as a trust layer—ensuring transparency, traceability, and tamper resistance in the model's aggregation process, while smart contracts handle incentive management, reputation tracking, and secure orchestration.

2.4.1 DECENTRALIZED AGGREGATION THROUGH BLOCKCHAIN

In blockchain-assisted FL, the aggregation of local model updates is no longer the responsibility of a single central node. Instead, aggregation decisions are reached through distributed consensus mechanisms, enabling all participating nodes (or miners) to verify, record, and validate updates.

Early studies, such as the work [25] on the BLADE-FL framework, demonstrate how blockchain can fully decentralize the aggregation workflow. In BLADE-FL, each client performs both *local model training* and *block mining*. Once local updates are generated, they are shared across a peer-to-peer (P2P) network and aggregated according to rules specified in an on-chain smart contract. This contract encodes all key parameters of the FL task—such as the reward structure, aggregation rule, and reputation thresholds—thereby removing the need for a trusted coordinator.

Each new aggregation result is recorded as a block that is verified by consensus (e.g., Proof-of-Work or Proof-of-Stake). Because all model updates and their provenance are stored immutably on the ledger, the entire learning process becomes auditable and tamper-proof.

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Furthermore, blockchain consensus enables self-correction: if any node behaves maliciously or submits anomalous gradients, others can verify and reject its contribution before final aggregation.

2.4.2 SMART CONTRACTS AND INCENTIVE MECHANISMS

One of the blockchain's major contributions to FL lies in automated trust management. Smart contracts not only control task publication and participant selection but also handle dynamic incentives. As highlighted in [26], their *systematic survey of BFL systems*, smart contracts can fairly distribute rewards based on contribution quality (e.g., model accuracy gain, Shapley value, or validation score), while simultaneously penalizing uncooperative or “lazy” clients.

In the BLADE-FL architecture, for instance, a task publisher deposits a reward pool when initiating an FL task. Clients who train and successfully verify their models receive tokens proportional to their contribution, whereas untrustworthy nodes—detected via validation or watermarking schemes—are excluded from future rounds. This automated, auditable incentive structure promotes fair participation and discourages free-riding or model plagiarism.

2.4.3 CONSENSUS PROTOCOLS FOR SECURE AGGREGATION

Different blockchain-based FL systems employ different consensus protocols to ensure agreement on aggregated results:

- Probabilistic consensus (e.g., Proof-of-Work or Proof-of-Stake) offers high scalability and is common in public networks but can be energy-intensive.
- Deterministic consensus (e.g., Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance – PBFT) ensures faster convergence and is ideal for permissioned consortium settings like enterprise or 6G edge networks.
- Hybrid consensus (e.g., Algorand, Biscotti) combines both approaches to balance efficiency and security, often by selecting a committee of trusted workers to validate models.

According to [26], these consensus designs are fundamental to achieving Byzantine-robust aggregation, where malicious nodes cannot arbitrarily alter the global model. For instance, Biscotti integrates *Proof-of-Federation* (PoF), which selects committee members based on their contribution level rather than stake, enhancing both fairness and model integrity.

2.4.4 AGGREGATION ARCHITECTURES

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Blockchain-based FL systems typically adopt one of three aggregation architectures—each with different scalability and security trade-offs:

1. Parameter-Server (PS) Architecture – Retains a central aggregator but uses blockchain as a trusted audit trail. While it ensures high consistency, it remains semi-centralized and limited by the aggregator’s resources.
2. All-Reduce Architecture – Fully decentralized; all clients participate in training and aggregation equally. It improves robustness but suffers from higher communication costs. Hierarchical versions (e.g., PIRATE) reduce this overhead via committee-based consensus.
3. Gossip Architecture – Lightweight and scalable; nodes exchange updates only with selected neighbours. Consensus determines which model is published globally. Examples such as BytoChain and BFDS improve this with “Proof-of-Accuracy” and “Proof-of-Training-Quality” schemes that select the best local model as the global update.

These architectures are often combined with tolerance-based (e.g., Krum, Multi-Krum, Bulyan) or detection-based (e.g., PSF, RONI, credit-score) aggregation rules to filter out poisoned or low-quality updates before they influence the global model.

2.4.5 SECURITY, PRIVACY, AND RESOURCE CONSIDERATIONS

BFL not only decentralizes aggregation but also addresses key security and privacy concerns. Local Differential Privacy (LDP) and homomorphic encryption are commonly integrated to safeguard model parameters from inference attacks, as seen in DeepChain and PBFL. However, these protections introduce computational and communication overheads, motivating recent work (e.g., BLADE-FL) on adaptive noise mechanisms and resource-optimized mining strategies to balance privacy and performance.

An emerging challenge is the detection of lazy or plagiarizing clients who attempt to gain rewards without contributing to the computation. BLADE-FL introduces a pseudo-noise watermarking approach—embedding unique signatures in model updates to identify duplicated or tampered parameters—demonstrating near-perfect detection rates in experimental settings.

2.5 LESSONS LEARNED FROM TASK 4.3 AND THEIR INCORPORATION INTO TASK 4.4 FEDERATED AI/ML ARCHITECTURE

1. Containerization, Virtualization, and Distributed Confidential Execution

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Task 4.3 demonstrated that modern 6G orchestration relies fundamentally on virtualization, lightweight containerization, and distributed deployment across heterogeneous compute nodes. The key insight for Task 4.4 is that federated AI/ML inherits the same operational realities: clients, aggregators, and auxiliary ML services must be deployable across varied edge–cloud systems that differ in CPU architecture, memory footprint, and trust guarantees. The ability to run FL components (training scripts, gradient compressors, secure aggregation services) inside containers enables portability and uniform lifecycle management, while CVM-based confidential containers ensure that model updates, sensitive training pipelines, or DP noise sampling processes remain isolated from the underlying infrastructure. Thus, the orchestration primitives from T4.3 container scheduling, isolation, lifecycle automation, and cross-platform execution become the foundation on which distributed FL tasks are reliably deployed, scaled, and securely executed.

2. Intelligent Orchestration and Runtime-Aware Scheduling

T4.3 showed that orchestration is no longer static: Kubernetes and related orchestrators rely on runtime metrics (CPU load, memory pressure, network delay, trustworthiness, and integrity state) to guide placement and scaling of workloads. This is directly transferable to federated learning in T4.4, where training performance and trust levels must dynamically inform scheduling decisions. For example, nodes with lower latency and sufficient compute can be selected for time-sensitive FL rounds, while nodes with stronger trust measurements (e.g., passing attestation) are prioritized for tasks involving sensitive model segments. Lessons from intent-based orchestration in T4.3 further guide T4.4 to adopt policy-driven FL scheduling, where FL clients' participation is gated on satisfying integrity, privacy, and hardware-capability constraints. Runtime metric integration learned in T4.3, therefore, becomes essential for building an adaptive FL workflow that selects optimal nodes, avoids weak or compromised devices, and responds to load variations across the network.

3. Confidential Orchestration, TEEs, and Remote Attestation

A central contribution of T4.3 is the mapping of confidential orchestration flows using TEEs, confidential containers, remote attestation, and trust propagation. For FL in T4.4, this becomes a critical precondition for trustworthy participation: before a client contributes gradients or receives global model updates, the aggregator must verify that the client runs inside a trusted enclave or CVM with the expected software stack. Likewise, clients must validate the integrity of the aggregator before sending sensitive updates. T4.3 established practical attestation workflows using the CoCo Trustee architecture, Key Broker Service, attestation evidence appraisal, and reference value providers. T4.4 directly reuses these mechanisms to establish mutual attestation between FL participants. This ensures that model training is executed only in verified environments, preventing insider attacks, malicious platform operators, or compromised nodes from participating in the FL pipeline.

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Thus, the attestation architecture from T4.3 becomes the trust backbone for federated learning.

4. Confidential Computing Deployment Models and Enclave-Based FL

T4.3 evaluated multiple confidential computing platforms: Intel SGX, Intel TDX, AMD SEV-SNP, ARM CCA, TrustZone, RISC-V Keystone, and FPGA TEEs. The lesson for T4.4 is that **federated learning must be designed for platform heterogeneity**, since FL clients will be executed on everything from high-performance cloud servers to constrained IoT/edge nodes. T4.3's analysis shows that TEEs differ in memory footprint, isolation granularity, supported languages, attestation formats, and container compatibility. For T4.4, this means that FL workflows must adaptively choose which components run inside TEEs (e.g., DP gradient computation, local model updates), which can be performed using HE/SMPC outside the enclave, and how to distribute critical versus non-critical code across secure and non-secure regions. Lessons from T4.3, therefore, guide T4.4 toward a **hybrid confidential FL pipeline**, balancing enclave execution, secure cryptography, and performance constraints across heterogeneous nodes in a 6G environment.

5. Multi-Domain Orchestration and Cross-Operator Federated Learning

T4.3 highlighted that 6G orchestration is inherently multi-domain: services span multiple operators, administrative boundaries, and heterogeneous infrastructures, requiring secure cross-domain cooperation. This observation directly informs T4.4, as federated learning often involves multiple stakeholders training a shared global model without sharing raw data. T4.3's lessons on zero-trust cross-domain orchestration, attested communication, and decentralized trust enable T4.4 to build federated learning pipelines where clients belong to different organizations, facilities, or network operators. The same principles distributed trust, policy-driven workload placement, mutual attestation, and remote verification ensure that FL operates securely across domains and that updates shared by one stakeholder cannot compromise others. Thus, multi-domain orchestration from T4.3 becomes essential for enabling cross-operator federated learning in WP5 use cases.

6. Protecting the Orchestration Layer from ML-Specific Threats

T4.3 identified new attack vectors introduced by ML-based orchestration itself (data poisoning, evasion, model leakage, misconfiguration through AI-driven automation). These lessons directly carry over to T4.4, where malicious FL clients may attempt to poison the shared model, perform model inversion, or exploit vulnerabilities in the aggregator. T4.3's analysis stresses the need for continuous verification of orchestrated ML workloads, dependency integrity, and supply-chain validation, which aligns precisely with T4.4's need to validate client updates via zero-knowledge proofs, anomaly detection, provenance tracking, or DP auditing. As T4.3 emphasizes, secure orchestration is not only about

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protecting the platform but also about protecting the ML processes executed within it, which shapes T4.4's defences against adversarial behaviour in federated learning.

7. Data Provenance, Integrity, and Secure Collaboration

A major insight from T4.3 concerns the importance of data provenance, distributed ledgers, and integrity-preserving collaboration across entities. For T4.4, federated learning benefits directly from these mechanisms: model updates must be traceable, auditable, and cryptographically bound to their origin to detect poisoning, Sybil attacks, or tampering. T4.3's findings on leveraging DLTs for provenance, combined with cryptographic binding of metadata, guide T4.4 in implementing secure FL metadata pipelines, where updates include verifiable lineage, integrity proofs, and traceability across distributed 6G ecosystems. Provenance's role in orchestration thus maps naturally to trustworthiness in federated learning.

8. Interoperability, Scalability, and Edge-Cloud Continuum Constraints

T4.3 showed that confidential orchestration must support diverse platforms from powerful cloud nodes to constrained IoT devices and remain interoperable across CPU architectures, software stacks, and trust models. For T4.4, this translates into designing FL algorithms and pipelines that are robust to inconsistent compute availability, heterogeneous trust levels, intermittent connectivity, and varied attestation support. T4.3's lessons on the limitations of CoCo on small edge devices, the need for hybrid enclave cryptographic designs, and the scalability constraints of Kubernetes-inspired orchestration inform T4.4 about when and where to place optimizer updates, gradient computation tasks, or secure aggregation functions. FL must therefore integrate edge-aware resource management mechanisms learned from T4.3 to function reliably over the 6G compute continuum.

3 REQUIREMENTS FOR FEDERATED AI/ML IN 6G

3.1 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS (SCALABLE ORCHESTRATION, HETEROGENEITY HANDLING)

Federated AI/ML in 6G must operate across a highly heterogeneous and dynamic compute continuum, spanning IoT nodes, edge servers, private enterprise clouds, public cloud infrastructures, and multi-operator environments. This creates a set of fundamental functional requirements that must be satisfied for Task 4.4 to support reliable, secure, and high-performance distributed training on a scale.

1. Scalable Orchestration Across Distributed 6G Infrastructure

Federated learning requires the ability to coordinate large numbers of training clients, potentially tens of thousands of devices per round, across diverse administrative domains and variable network conditions. This demands orchestration mechanisms capable of scalable participant discovery, resource allocation, scheduling, and coordination of parallel training jobs with minimal latency overhead. The orchestration layer must support efficient round management, adaptive joining and leaving of clients, and policy-driven selection of participating nodes based on availability, trust level, attestation results, device performance, and network state. To meet 6G requirements, orchestration must also support rapid elasticity, allowing FL tasks to scale up or down in response to shifts in traffic load, energy constraints, or service-level objectives. Ultimately, FL orchestrators must maintain high throughput and robustness even under massive-scale deployments typical of 6G industrial, vehicular, and IoT scenarios.

2. Handling Device, Hardware, and Trust Heterogeneity

6G environments are inherently heterogeneous, with devices varying widely in compute power, memory footprint, energy availability, network connectivity, and security capabilities. Federated learning operations must therefore be executable across a spectrum ranging from resource-constrained IoT nodes to high-performance edge clusters. This requires flexible workload decomposition that accounts for client capabilities, allowing lightweight local training on small devices while enabling more complex tasks on capable nodes. Additionally, heterogeneous confidential computing capabilities mean that some devices will support TEEs, confidential VMs, or hardware-backed attestation, while others rely solely on cryptographic protection such as HE or SMPC. FL must adaptively select training strategies, cryptographic schemes, and communication patterns based on each node's hardware capabilities and trust posture. Moreover, heterogeneity in data distributions, model architectures, and domain-specific sampling patterns must be addressed through personalized FL techniques, client clustering, or adaptive model

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partitioning. Support for heterogeneity is therefore critical to ensure that FL in 6G remains inclusive, efficient, and secure across the entire compute continuum.

3.2 SECURITY & PRIVACY REQUIREMENTS (CONFIDENTIALITY, INTEGRITY, FAIRNESS)

Federated AI/ML in 6G must operate in a distributed, multi-stakeholder environment where data remains decentralized, computation spans heterogeneous trust domains, and adversarial behaviour may originate from clients, aggregators, or the underlying infrastructure. As a result, strong security and privacy guarantees are essential for maintaining trustworthy learning outcomes. These guarantees must address confidentiality of data and model updates, integrity of the learning process and infrastructure, and fairness in the resulting models when trained across diverse data populations. The requirements outlined below describe the foundational protections that Task 4.4 must provide in order to support secure and privacy-preserving federated intelligence in 6G systems.

1. Confidentiality of Data, Models, and Execution

Federated learning inherently limits raw data exposure by keeping training data at the client side, but this alone is insufficient in 6G environments where network operators, cloud providers, and cross-domain stakeholders may not fully trust one another. Confidentiality must extend beyond raw data to include gradients, intermediate model updates, metadata, and the execution environment itself. This requires guaranteed protection of sensitive information both in transit and at rest, as well as during computation. Techniques such as confidential computing, encrypted training (e.g., homomorphic encryption), secure multi-party aggregation, and differential privacy must ensure that adversaries cannot infer sensitive attributes through update analysis or system-level inspection. Protection must also cover Metadata such as participation frequency or model contribution patterns that may reveal behavioural information. Ensuring confidentiality prevents leakage across organizational boundaries, protects user data under strict regulatory constraints, and preserves commercial or strategic confidentiality inherent in 6G vertical use cases.

2. Integrity of Training, Infrastructure, and Model Outputs

In a distributed and partially untrusted federated learning ecosystem, the integrity of the training process is essential to prevent poisoning attacks, model corruption, or unauthorized modification of system behaviour. Integrity requirements apply at multiple layers: the device layer (ensuring that clients run verified software inside trusted execution environments), the communication layer (ensuring that updates are authentic and untampered), the aggregation layer (ensuring that only valid, non-malicious updates are included), and the final model (ensuring that the training outcome reflects legitimate data contributions). Remote attestation, verifiable cryptographic protocols, update validation (including

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structural, statistical, or zero-knowledge-based correctness proofs), and provenance tracking must collectively ensure that the learning pipeline cannot be manipulated by adversarial clients or compromised orchestration components. Integrity protections must also prevent rollback attacks, enforce proper execution of DP noise mechanisms, and enable detection of anomalous or suspicious contributions. This ensures that 6G AI/ML systems remain robust, trustworthy, and resistant to manipulation even in adversarial multi-domain deployments.

3. Fairness, Non-Discrimination, and Bias Mitigation

Federated learning in 6G introduces fairness challenges because training data is distributed across diverse populations, devices, and organizations, often with non-IID distributions and unequal representation. These conditions can lead to biased global models that underperform minority groups, low-resource clients, or sectors with weak connectivity or limited compute capabilities. Ensuring fairness requires mechanisms that balance contribution weighting, mitigate client-level bias, detect disparate impacts, and prevent training behaviours that systematically exclude or disadvantage particular participants. Privacy-preserving fairness auditing, secure aggregation of fairness metrics, and incentive mechanisms that prevent strategic manipulation must be incorporated without compromising confidentiality. Since fairness risks may be exacerbated when FL spans different operators, enterprises, or regulatory domains as expected in 6G verticals FL algorithms must provide guarantees that model decisions remain equitable across the heterogeneous user base. Ensuring fairness is therefore a core requirement for trustworthy, transparent, and socially responsible federated AI/ML in 6G.

3.3 ORAN SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS (MULTI-BS COORDINATION, EDGE CONSTRAINTS, AND TRUST)

Although Task 4.4 does not directly implement federated learning within an ORAN system, ORAN still represents a realistic and representative environment for future 6G deployments. Since WP5 use cases rely on ORAN-based testbeds, it is important that the federated AI/ML framework designed in this task remains conceptually compatible with ORAN principles. This section, therefore, outlines the ORAN-related requirements that influence how the architecture should be designed, without implying a full ORAN integration within this task.

3.3.1 ARCHITECTURAL REQUIREMENTS FOR DISTRIBUTED RAN INTELLIGENCE

ORAN introduces a disaggregated RAN architecture where intelligence is distributed across multiple components, such as the Near-Real-Time and Non-Real-Time RICs. In an FL context, these distributed RICs and base-station elements could naturally act as federated clients, each holding its own localized datasets derived from radio conditions, mobility information,

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or user traffic behaviour. For Task 4.4, this implies that the FL framework should be capable of supporting participation from multiple heterogeneous nodes and remain flexible enough to operate across a multi-base-station topology. Furthermore, ORAN's emphasis on open interfaces such as A1, E2, and O1 suggests that any future integration with ORAN-based controllers would benefit from an architecture that does not rely on proprietary or tightly coupled communication patterns. Ensuring architectural compatibility at this conceptual level makes it easier for Task 4.4 outputs to be deployable in ORAN-driven environments if required by future steps or WP5 demonstrations.

3.3.2 PERFORMANCE AND EDGE RESOURCE CONSTRAINTS

ORAN systems typically operate under strict latency, timing, and resource constraints, especially within Near-Real-Time RIC components that must process and react to network events quickly. For federated learning, this means the architecture must be able to accommodate shorter training or update cycles if used within ORAN and should be resilient to variability in connectivity between nodes. Edge nodes in ORAN also tend to have limited processing budgets compared to cloud resources, so any federated learning design intended for potential ORAN environments should support efficient local training, lightweight model updates, and the possibility of asynchronous participation. Designing Task 4.4 with awareness of these practical constraints ensures that the federated learning approach remains feasible and relevant in telecom-grade scenarios even if the implementation is not directly embedded within ORAN in this phase.

3.3.3 TRUST, SECURITY, AND PRIVACY REQUIREMENTS

Because ORAN promotes multi-vendor openness and interoperability, trust management becomes a critical requirement for any distributed learning approach applied within such an environment. Different network components may belong to different administrative domains or vendors, which means that the federated learning system must assume a partially trusted ecosystem. Therefore, if FL were used in an ORAN deployment, all model exchanges would need to be transmitted over secure and attested channels, allowing nodes to verify both the origin and the integrity of received updates. Sensitive radio and mobility data would also need protection through confidential execution environments or privacy-enhancing technologies. Trust and privacy enablers developed under WP2—such as Differential Privacy, Homomorphic Encryption, Zero-Knowledge Proofs, and Decentralized Identifiers—are especially relevant in this context. In addition, mechanisms such as blockchain-based audit trails and decentralized reputation systems could help verify contributions and discourage malicious or low-quality updates in a multi-stakeholder ORAN environment.

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In summary, while Task 4.4 is not integrating directly into ORAN, the FL architecture must still be aware of ORAN-specific constraints to ensure future applicability and alignment with the 6G ecosystem envisioned in the project. ORAN represents an important reference environment for distributed AI in telecom networks, and aligning our requirements with its principles ensures that the Task 4.4 framework can be adopted or validated within WP5 use cases without major architectural changes. This compatibility strengthens the long-term relevance of the work and provides flexibility for future extensions toward ORAN-based AI deployments.

3.4 THREAT MODELS

To design a secure and trustworthy FL framework for 6G environments, it is essential to understand the potential threat landscape and the assumptions under which the system must operate. Federated Learning inherently decentralizes training across heterogeneous devices and administrative domains, making it exposed to a wide range of adversarial behaviours that may target data confidentiality, model integrity, fairness, or system availability. In the context of Task 4.4, the threat model does not focus on adversaries capable of breaking fundamental cryptographic primitives; rather, it considers realistic attackers who exploit vulnerabilities in FL workflows, communication channels, or aggregation pipelines. The following subsections provide a structured overview of the most relevant threat categories

3.4.1 HONEST-BUT-CURIOUS ADVERSARIES

An honest but curious adversary follows the prescribed protocol but attempts to infer private information from the data it receives. In federated learning settings, this typically includes trying to extract sensitive patterns from shared gradients, model weights, or metadata such as training time and updating magnitude. Even without direct access to raw datasets, gradient inversion attacks—such as Deep Leakage from Gradients (DLG)—have demonstrated that an adversary observing standard FL updates can reconstruct portions of the original input data. In 6G scenarios, this could reveal sensitive contextual information, such as user mobility patterns, radio fingerprints, or network usage profiles. Consequently, any FL system deployed in such environments must consider that seemingly benign participants may attempt to infer data indirectly through model updates.

3.4.2 MALICIOUS CLIENTS

Malicious clients intentionally deviate from the federated learning protocol to manipulate the global model or degrade system performance. One common strategy involves data poisoning, where a client introduces corrupted or misleading samples into its local dataset, causing the aggregated model to produce biased or harmful outputs. Another common threat

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is model poisoning, where a client directly manipulates its gradients or parameters before submission, potentially introducing backdoors into the global model. Free-rider attacks also fall into this category, where a client uploads random or reused updates to gain access to global model improvements without performing any genuine local training. These attacks are especially concerning in open or multi-stakeholder environments and require robust aggregation and trust mechanisms to mitigate.

3.4.3 COMPROMISED OR MALICIOUS AGGREGATORS

In traditional FL, the aggregator has a central and highly privileged role, making it an attractive target for attackers. A compromised aggregator can selectively drop or modify client updates, alter the global model, or infer private information from unencrypted gradients. While Task 4.4 introduces blockchain-based consensus mechanisms to remove the single point of failure and decentralize aggregation, the threat of malicious aggregators remains relevant when considering partial, hierarchical, or hybrid aggregation structures that may still exist in real deployments. Even when aggregation is decentralized, some forms of validation or partial aggregation may still rely on semi-trusted nodes that must be protected against compromise.

3.4.4 COMMUNICATION CHANNEL THREATS

The distributed nature of FL inherently relies on communication between clients and the orchestrator or blockchain network. Without strong protection, these communication channels may become targets for eavesdropping, tampering, or replay attacks. Adversaries could capture model updates, inject falsified messages, or disrupt synchronization across clients. In 6G and edge computing environments, where devices may rely on wireless links or dynamic network topologies, such threats become even more pronounced. Secure, attested communication channels—integrating TLS, mutual authentication, and potentially TEE-based attestation—are essential to ensuring that updates cannot be intercepted or modified in transit.

3.4.5 INSIDER THREATS AND CROSS-DOMAIN ADVERSARIES

6G and ORAN deployments often involve multiple vendors, operators, and administrative domains. This increases the likelihood of insider threats—participants who appear legitimate but behave maliciously due to misconfiguration, negligence, or intentional exploitation. Such adversaries may possess elevated privileges, deeper system access, or detailed protocol knowledge, making detection more difficult than with external attacks. Moreover, when federated learning spans multiple trust domains, adversaries may exploit misalignments in policies, model-update rules, or privacy configurations to gain an advantage or disrupt training. Addressing these threats requires clear trust boundaries,

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identity management mechanisms such as Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), and continuous auditing through blockchain-based provenance tracking.

In summary, the threat landscape for federated learning in 6G ecosystems is broad and multifaceted, encompassing both passive adversaries who seek to infer sensitive information and active adversaries who aim to corrupt or disrupt the model. Understanding these threats is essential for designing the secure orchestration, cryptographic integration, and decentralized trust mechanisms developed in Task 4.4. The architectural decisions presented in later chapters address these vulnerabilities through confidential computation, robust aggregation strategies, secure communication channels, and blockchain-based accountability, ensuring that the resulting framework remains trustworthy even in partially trusted or adversarial environments.

4 ARCHITECTURE AND TECHNOLOGY ENABLERS

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW (CLOUD-EDGE ORCHESTRATOR, CLIENTS, BLOCKCHAIN LAYER)

The overall architecture designed under Task 4.4 – Federated AI/ML builds upon the confidential orchestration framework established in Task 4.3 and extends it with federated learning (FL) and blockchain-enabled trust mechanisms. It integrates technology enablers developed in WP2, such as Differential Privacy (DP), Homomorphic Encryption (HE), Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), and Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), which collectively strengthen data confidentiality and identity management within the federated ecosystem. At the same time, it leverages WP3's AI/ML methods to ensure model efficiency, adaptability, and fairness under heterogeneous and non-IID conditions. The validated outcomes of Task 4.4 will feed into WP5 use cases, where the framework will be demonstrated in real 6G/ORAN-enabled environments.

The overarching objective is to provide a secure, privacy-preserving, and auditable AI training framework capable of operating seamlessly across multi-domain 6G and edge infrastructures. Figure 1 illustrates the high-level architecture comprising three main layers: the Cloud-Edge Orchestrator, the Federated Clients, and the Blockchain Layer, interconnected through cryptographically secured and policy-aware interfaces.

4.1.1 OVERALL SYSTEM CONCEPT

The architecture separates policy and decision logic, client validation and secure aggregation, federated coordination, and confidential execution into clearly defined functional layers. This separation ensures that training tasks can be executed close to the data source while maintaining end-to-end protection, verifiability, and compliance with security and privacy requirements.

The system enables confidential client execution through encrypted or TEE-based containers, supports strong identity and platform attestation using the DID, VC, and ZKP mechanisms from WP2, and applies blockchain-backed secure aggregation to eliminate reliance on a central trusted server. It additionally incorporates fair and resource-aware client selection, as well as operator visibility and real-time analytics for policy-driven responses.

This modular design allows each component to evolve independently while remaining interoperable, creating an extensible and trustworthy federated learning pipeline that aligns with the broader Confidential6G architecture.

Figure 1: Federated AI/ML System architecture

4.1.2 OPERATOR MONITORING & POLICY INTERFACE

The Operator Monitoring & Policy Interface forms the topmost layer of the architecture and provides system-wide visibility, policy enforcement, and operational control. This layer interacts closely with the underlying orchestration and security modules to ensure that the federated learning process behaves as expected in dynamic and distributed environments. Through a dedicated Monitoring, Visualization, and Control Interface, operators can track

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system performance, analyse client behaviour, inspect the evolution of model updates, and trigger interventions when anomalies or deviations are detected.

This layer also incorporates an Analytics and Decisions Engine, which continuously evaluates telemetry data, resource conditions, and threat indicators. Insights from this engine influence downstream orchestration decisions and allow policies such as client eligibility, privacy budgets, aggregation thresholds, or trust criteria to be adapted in real time. The interaction between this interface and the Security Orchestration module ensures that updated operator-defined policies are consistently enforced throughout the entire training workflow, from client selection to model aggregation.

4.1.3 SECURITY, VALIDATION, AND AGGREGATION LAYER

The Security, Validation, and Aggregation Layer establishes trust before any client participates in training and ensures the integrity of the aggregated model. This layer begins with the Client Validation module, which uses cryptographic identity mechanisms from WP2—including Decentralized Identifiers (DID), Verifiable Credentials (VC), and Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP)—to authenticate clients and verify that they belong to trusted domains. This validation step reduces the risk of malicious or misconfigured participants entering the federated learning process.

Alongside identity verification, a Platform Attestor confirms that each client's execution environment meets the confidentiality and integrity requirements set by the orchestrator. This includes verifying that confidential containers or TEEs are active and properly configured. Together, these mechanisms produce a vetted pool of clients that can safely join training rounds.

Model updates from validated clients are processed within the Secure Aggregation Module, which leverages blockchain-based consensus to remove the need for a single trusted aggregator. Instead, model updates are recorded and validated through a distributed and tamper-resistant ledger. This ensures auditability, prevents undetected manipulation of parameters, and provides accountability for both honest and adversarial behaviour. The aggregation result is then transmitted to the orchestrator as a verified global model update.

4.1.4 FEDERATION & ORCHESTRATION LAYER

The Federation & Orchestration Layer coordinates the execution of training tasks across distributed clients. At its core is the Federated Coordinator, which manages round initiation, model dispatch, encrypted update collection, and convergence decisions. It orchestrates communication flows between selected clients and integrates policy directives and validation results from the upper layers.

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A key component of this layer is the Client Selection Module, which accounts for heterogeneity in compute capabilities, network stability, fairness requirements, and device reliability. By evaluating these factors, architecture ensures that the federated learning process remains equitable, efficient, and resilient to struggling or unreliable participants.

The layer also incorporates a Resource and Energy Manager responsible for optimizing computing load and energy consumption across participating nodes. This is particularly important for edge deployments where resources are constrained. Once clients are selected and resources allocated, the Federated Coordinator triggers the Confidential Container Instantiation process, launching isolated and encrypted execution environments on each client. These containers protect local data and prevent leakage of intermediate training artefacts.

4.1.5 INFRASTRUCTURE LAYER

The Infrastructure Layer provides the secure execution foundation for local training. It hosts Encrypted Containers or TEE-backed environments in which privacy-preserving computations take place. These confidential runtimes incorporate privacy-enhancing techniques such as Differential Privacy and Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), supported by WP2. By doing so, the architecture ensures that raw data never leaves the device and that model updates remain protected even during local training.

Once training is complete, encrypted model updates flow back to the Security and Aggregation layer through secure communication channels. The infrastructure layer thereby forms the final, trusted environment where local computations occur, ensuring end-to-end confidentiality and integrity throughout the federated learning pipeline.

4.2 CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION FOR FEDERATED LEARNING

4.2.1 OVERVIEW

Secure orchestration must ensure that the entire Federated Learning (FL) workflow, from software deployment and local training to global aggregation and iteration, as well as to final production model distribution and inference, is protected against threats such as data leakage, model poisoning, and unauthorized access. This is inherently challenging because attackers can develop new attack vectors that were not anticipated in the original threat model. Despite this, certain foundational security principles should always be enforced:

- **Isolation and access control** - Mechanisms must prevent unauthorized access to sensitive data and resources.
- **Node integrity verification** - All nodes participating in orchestration should have their integrity verified before joining the workflow.

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- **Protection against malicious service providers** - Threat models often assume that even infrastructure providers (e.g., cloud service providers) could act maliciously, so safeguards must address this risk.

Traditionally, FL relies on privacy-preserving local training, ensuring raw data never leaves the data owner's environment. This assumes that local processing is inherently secure because the computing platform is under the data owner's control. However, privacy-preserving approaches, including differential privacy, face two challenges. First, the aggregating servers, which are not in the data owner's control, may be able to retrieve information from aggregates of local data. This threat cannot be fully mitigated with differential privacy, which reduces models' accuracy. Second, the local data – the client-side of FL – may also be on platforms that are not under the data owner's control. Modern data processing increasingly leverages cloud-based services, requiring users to upload local data and trust the cloud provider.

Confidential Computing addresses these challenges by protecting raw data even when processed in the cloud. It uses hardware-based Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) to ensure both data and code confidentiality and integrity during computation. Furthermore, confidential computing can be extended to edge and IoT nodes, reducing data transfers and supporting strict latency requirements that are critical for real-time applications.

4.2.2 ISOLATION MECHANISMS

Hardware-based TEEs provide isolated environments for confidential computing workloads, protecting them from the rest of the system and reducing exposure to attacks. TEEs can also mitigate risks from malicious service providers, though they require trust in hardware vendors and their TEE implementations.

TEEs can offer isolation at different levels:

- **Virtual machine level** - Confidential virtual machines run an entire operating system, including the kernel, in an isolated environment that is protected even from hypervisors. Examples include AMD SEV-SNP and Intel TDX, which enable secure VM-based deployments.
- **Container level** - Confidential containers execute workloads inside TEEs configured with container orchestration tools. Containers share the host kernel, which introduces potential side-channel risks and requires trust in the kernel owner. The Confidential Containers (CoCo) open-source project is a notable example.
- **Application level** - Confidential applications (or processes) run in highly restricted environments. For instance, ARM TrustZone, widely used in embedded and mobile systems, supports Trusted Applications running in Secure World, isolated from the Normal World.

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These approaches differ in resource requirements and workload portability. Virtual machines allow the deployment of unmodified workloads but consume significant resources since an entire OS, including the kernel, is instantiated for each workload. Containers require container configuration, but are more resource-efficient because only workload-related components are instantiated. However, shared kernels introduce trust and security challenges. Application-level isolation often requires substantial code modifications and partitioning of workloads so that only critical components run inside the TEE. TEEs in this category are typically also resource-constrained.

Hardware-based confidential computing shifts trust from service providers to hardware vendors. While TEEs are widely adopted, they rely on the correctness and security of vendor implementations. A fully software-based alternative to TEE-based confidential computing is Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), which eliminates hardware trust requirements by enabling computation on encrypted data. However, FHE remains highly resource-intensive and is generally impractical for most real-world deployments.

4.2.3 CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION

Orchestration refers to the automated process of deploying, managing, and scaling computing workloads across available resources. It covers the entire workload lifecycle, ensuring optimal resource utilization while meeting performance and security requirements.

A widely adopted orchestration platform is Kubernetes [27], an open-source system designed for containerized workloads, especially in cloud environments. A Kubernetes cluster consists of multiple computing nodes that serve as deployment targets. Each node can host several pods, which are the smallest deployable units. In practice, a pod typically encapsulates one or more containers.

Orchestration decisions are driven by system metrics and constraints, such as CPU and memory utilization at both node and pod levels. For example, workloads should not be scheduled on nodes experiencing high CPU load or memory pressure. Decisions may also consider data transfer costs and latency requirements, which can lead to deploying workloads closer to edge or IoT nodes to meet real-time constraints.

Confidential orchestration extends these principles to workloads that require strong confidentiality guarantees. It leverages TEEs to protect data in use, even in untrusted environments [28].

In the context of Federated Learning, this changes the traditional trust model. Instead of assuming local nodes are fully trusted and aggregation nodes are less trusted, confidential orchestration binds trust to hardware vendors rather than service providers. This enables

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secure enclaves to exist across multiple system locations, including cloud, edge, and IoT nodes.

By combining TEEs with orchestration, users can minimize data transfers, meet strict latency requirements, and maintain confidentiality throughout the workflow, even when workloads run outside the data owner’s infrastructure.

4.2.4 CONFIDENTIAL CONTAINERS

If orchestration targets a heterogeneous environment, such as the cloud-edge-IoT continuum, the orchestration framework must support multiple platforms and isolation mechanisms. The Confidential Containers (CoCo) project [29] provides a flexible framework that enables orchestration of confidential workloads across different TEE models, including both Virtual Machine-based and Application (process) based approaches.

Figure 2: Confidential Containers project defines two architecture alternatives.

4.2.5 INTEGRITY VERIFICATION

Large distributed systems must ensure that devices connecting to trusted entities are genuine, authorized nodes running unmodified firmware. Remote attestation provides a

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mechanism to verify both the identity and integrity of these devices. It builds on a measurement mechanism that utilizes trusted hardware like Trusted Platform Module (TPM) to store measurement data integrity information and to sign messages. Remote attestation allows a remote verifier, such as a service provider, to confirm the integrity of a connecting system before granting access or delivering services. Mutual remote attestation extends this concept by allowing both parties to validate each other's integrity, ensuring trust in both directions.

To achieve interoperability and consistency, remote attestation mechanisms and data formats need standardization. The IETF Remote Attestation Procedures (RATS) Working Group addresses this challenge by defining an architecture for remote attestation [30] and standardizing:

- Evidence and Attestation Result Formats
- Protocols for conveying evidence to a verifier and results to a relying party
- Formats for endorsements and reference values, including profiling or adapting existing standards for secure transmission to verifiers

IETF RATS aims to create a unified framework for secure attestation across diverse platforms and environments.

Figure 3: IETF RATS information flow and roles in remote attestation

4.2.6 FL ORCHESTRATION

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An orchestrator deploys and configures FL software. Own software is deployed on both client and (aggregating) servers. FL-specific configuration parameters that are adjusted during deployment or during operation may include:

- Adjusting the aggregation algorithm to ensure that the global model converges correctly, this may require the orchestrator to analyse contributing nodes and monitor the performance of the global model.
- Differential privacy budget that balances acceptable privacy loss against achieved model accuracy.
- Authentication and authorization data, certificates, and keying material, enabling mutual authentication between clients and servers or signing of models to authenticate their integrity.
- Client selection strategy for selecting a subset of clients for different training rounds (based, e.g., on factors like network connectivity, battery life, available computing resources, quality of local data). This includes reselection of new nodes in case of dropouts.
- Use of model compression or update frequency reduction to adapt the amount of transmitted communication
- Reacting to detected model poisoning cases, e.g., by removing corrupted nodes.

The orchestrator may also utilize confidentiality services and characteristics available in the devices. It can act as a trusted authority or security provisioning server that manages cryptographic keys managed in TEE.

4.3 FL ORCHESTRATION & EXECUTION

4.3.1 PERSONALIZED FEDERATED LEARNING FOR CONVERGENCE MAXIMIZATION ON NON-IID DATA DISTRIBUTIONS

Federated Learning (FL) enables collaborative training over decentralized, privacy-sensitive data, but its performance is severely impacted by non-IID client data, which causes skewed updates, slower convergence, and degraded global accuracy (see Figure 4), which illustrates the FL process and the non-IID data divergence).

Figure 4: (Left) Usual FL training procedure with FedAvg. (Right) FL's local weight divergence illustration in the presence of IID and non-IID data.

In this context, *Personalized FL* (PFL) addresses this heterogeneity by tailoring models to individual clients. The work [31] classifies state-of-the-art solutions for PFL into: (i) *regularization-based methods* that modify local objectives; and (ii) *selection-based methods* that choose which clients participate in training; the approach in this work belongs to the latter family.

This work leverages the Population Stability Index (PSI) [32], a metric widely used in credit scoring to detect distribution shifts, as an efficient and accurate measure of non-IIDness in FL and as a criterion to select more homogeneous client subsets, focusing on the particularly harmful case of label skew.

Building on this idea, this work proposes PSI-PFL, a PSI-based client selection strategy that mitigates non-IID-induced performance degradation and improves global model accuracy by up to 10% over state-of-the-art baselines, representing, to the best of current knowledge, the first use of PSI in FL both for heterogeneity quantification and client selection.

Proposed solution

The described PSI-PFL solution (see Figure 5) efficiently details the high-level training process where clients share label frequencies, the server computes the Population Stability Index (PSI) for each client and selects clients with PSI below a threshold for training.

Figure 5: High-level PSI-PFL training process.

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Considering the label skew case, the formula to calculate the PSI [32] for a client i is presented in the following equation:

$$PSI_i^L = \sum_{c=1}^C (P(y=c) - P_i(y=c)) \ln \left(\frac{P(y=c)}{P_i(y=c)} \right)$$

where $P(y=c)$ represents the global probability mass function (pmf) of the label y for class c , which is calculated by the server with the (aggregated) label frequencies received from the clients; $P_i(y=c)$ is the client i pmf of the label y for class c , and C is the maximum number of classes of y . Notice that the superscript L represents the calculations for the label skew case.

Given that PSI is calculated individually by each client, the non-IIDness quantification of the FL system in the label skew case can be determined by computing the weighted average, denoted as $WPSI^L$. Specifically, this is expressed by the following equation:

$$WPSI^L = \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{n_i}{N} PSI_i^L$$

where K is the total number of clients, n_i is the number of examples in the i^{th} client, and N is the total number of examples across all clients. The superscript L indicates that the calculation pertains to the label skew case. Notice that low values of PSI_i and $WPSI^L$ suggest a more homogeneous environment, whereas higher values indicate a greater degree of non-IID characteristics.

After calculating the PSI for each client, devices with PSI below a defined threshold τ are selected for training. Lower PSI values indicate more homogeneous data, so prioritizing these clients helps the global model better represent the population and avoid convergence issues caused by highly heterogeneous clients. The threshold τ is a key hyperparameter that needs careful tuning based on client characteristics using the following Algorithm 1:

Require: PSI values psi_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ clients, performance metric (e.g., global accuracy)

Ensure: Optimal threshold τ^*

- 1: Compute PSI for each client using Eq. 1
- 2: Determine candidate τ thresholds from the 10th, 25th, 50th, 75th, and 90th percentiles of $\{psi_i\}$
- 3: **for** each candidate threshold τ **do**
- 4: Select clients with $PSI \leq \tau$
- 5: Train the FL model with selected clients
- 6: Evaluate model performance (e.g., global accuracy)
- 7: **end for**
- 8: Select τ^* corresponding to the highest performance
- 9: **return** τ^*

Algorithm 1 PSI-PFL Algorithm for optimal threshold τ selection

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This methodology allows for a data-driven, systematic approach to threshold selection, ensuring that the chosen τ is well-suited to the specific characteristics of the client population. The efficacy of this approach is empirically validated in the following section.

Evaluation

We evaluate PSI-PFL across various datasets (tabular, image, and text), models, and data distributions. The details of the centralized datasets are summarized in Table 1.

Dataset	Modality	Task	# classes	# examples
ACS Income [Ding et al., 2021]	Tabular	Classify high /low salary	2	1,664,500
Dutch [Van der Laan, 2001]	Tabular	Classify high /low salary	2	60,420
CelebA [Liu et al., 2015]	Image	Detect smiling	2	202,599
Sent140 [Go et al., 2009]	Text	Sentiment analysis	3	1,600,000

Table 1 Characteristics of the analysed datasets

We employed a widely used partitioning protocol to simulate varying data distributions: Dirichlet [33]. This protocol controls the degree of non-IIDness through a single parameter (α), where smaller parameter values result in more heterogeneous client distributions.

For each dataset, we use a dedicated model version as explained in the following Table 2:

Layer	Description	Layer	Description	Layer	Description
Fully Connected Layer	(input size, 2)	Conv2D with Relu	(3, 8, 3, 1)	GloVe 6B Embeddings	(25,300)
		Max Pooling	(2, 2)	LSTM	(25, 10)
		Conv2D with Relu	(8, 16, 3, 1)	Fully Connected with Relu	(10)
		Max Pooling	(2, 2)	Fully Connected with Softmax	(2)
		Conv2D with Relu	(16, 32, 3, 1)		
		Max Pooling	(2, 2)		
		Fully Connected with Relu	(8 × 8 × 32)		

a)

b)

c)

Table 2 Model architecture used for ACSIncome and Dutch datasets(a), CelebA (b) and Sent140 (c)

In the upcoming metrics, we mainly use two metrics: accuracy and fairness. Accuracy quantifies the ratio of well-classified samples between the total number of samples and can be evaluated at the individual client level or in an aggregated manner to form the *Global accuracy* value. For fairness, we use the *Client Parity* (CP) metric, which requires that all FL clients achieve similar accuracy values (or loss values).

CP is often quantified as the maximum relative performance difference between clients:

$$CP = \frac{\max_{i,j=1}^K |\phi_i - \phi_j|}{\min_{i=1}^K \phi_i}$$

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Where ϕ_i corresponds to the local accuracy of the i^{th} client. In this case, smaller values of CP indicate higher client fairness.

The obtained results of applying PSI-PFL are summarized in the following text:

Figure 6: Global test accuracy obtained for all considered baselines in various scenarios varying the number of clients and the data heterogeneity (α parameter)

Figure 6 shows the average global accuracy of PSI-PFL and all baselines varying the number of clients, and the α parameter, along with the corresponding $WPSI^L$. PSI-PFL consistently outperforms the baselines, even under high non-IIDness, in up to 10% relative increase in global accuracy compared to HACCS and FedCLS, the most challenging competitors. The global accuracy of PSI-PFL has a small standard deviation (~ 0.02), indicating stable performance. Its performance improves in scenarios with more clients (e.g., 50 or 100). Results are consistent across the considered datasets (omitted for brevity).

Figure 7: Local test accuracy across clients for all the considered baselines in three distinct heterogeneity scenarios

Figure 7 presents the empirical cumulative distribution function (ECDF) of local accuracy for PSI-PFL and all baselines across varying α values. Notably, the PSI-PFL distribution aligns more closely with the CL (target) distribution than the baselines, highlighting its superior performance in terms of client fairness. Our PS-PFL solution achieved a CP=0.27 for the

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scenario with higher heterogeneity ($\alpha = 0.3$), by far the best value compared to the other baselines. Results are consistent across the considered datasets (omitted for brevity).

Conclusions

In this work, we propose the PSI-PFL framework, which leverages the PSI as a novel metric for client selection in non-IID PFL. Our findings demonstrate that PSI-PFL consistently outperforms state-of-the-art baselines by up to 10% relative increase in global accuracy while ensuring fairer local performance, reaching only a 3% average difference compared to the CL (target), making it a valuable tool for enhancing decentralized learning in heterogeneous environments.

4.3.2 PERSONALIZED TIER-AWARE FEDERATED LEARNING FOR NEXT-LOCATION PREDICTION WITH MOBILITY DATA

While Section 4.3.1 focused on mitigating non-IID label skew via PSI-PFL, the second line of work in this project addresses a complementary source of heterogeneity: the coupling between user mobility and device capabilities. Modern cellular networks host a diverse device population, spanning low-end terminals with limited computing capabilities and intermittent connectivity to high-end smartphones with stable bandwidth and richer mobility traces. These differences translate into tier-dependent trajectory statistics (e.g., sampling frequency, spatial coverage, typical speeds), which can bias a single global next-location predictor and degrade both accuracy and fairness across device classes. Similar tier-aware device stratification has been explored in TiFL [34].

The work described in this section leverages telecommunication network data enriched by Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS), an emerging technology for 6G networks that jointly exploits communication signals for high-precision sensing and positioning. JCAS enables fine-grained location and speed estimates directly within the network, moving from indirect indicators such as RSS time series toward near real-time, grid-level position information. This richer view of the radio environment is particularly suited to intelligent connected-vehicle scenarios, where accurate and timely mobility information underpins traffic-aware services, cooperative manoeuvres, and safety-critical decision-making [35]. In this context, we focus on two representative predictive tasks – traffic congestion prediction and cellular handover prediction – as building blocks for advanced vehicular connectivity.

To study the impact of this JCAS-enhanced, tier-dependent heterogeneity, we build a tier-aware FL framework for next-location prediction over real Mobile Network Operator (MNO) traces. Devices are grouped into three tiers (Low, Mid, High) based on hardware and connectivity attributes, and these tiers are used as a system-level prior when distributing data across silos and evaluating models. FL is essential in this setting because raw

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JCAS-based mobility traces are privacy-sensitive and often cannot be centralized at scale; instead, training must occur where the data resides, under heterogeneous compute and connectivity constraints. Our design explicitly embraces this heterogeneity: by running controlled FL experiments under different cross-silo tier configurations, we can study how imbalance and tier mixing affect both convergence and fairness of the learned models. This design allows us to go beyond aggregate metrics and explicitly quantify how different cross-silo tier configurations impact: (i) predictive performance for each tier, and (ii) fairness across tiers, in terms of error and accuracy gaps. The approach is fully compatible with the PSI-PFL ideas in Section 4.3.1: PSI can be used to quantify label skew, while tiers and JCAS-derived mobility profiles encode structural heterogeneity in the underlying device population and motivate the need for tier-aware FL. Such cross-network mobility heterogeneity has also been studied in multi-network FL settings [36].

Proposed solution

Problem formulation and data model

The target task is short-horizon next-location prediction over a discretized geographic grid. For each user, we construct sequences of past observations (e.g., timestamped cell or grid IDs enriched with contextual features such as time-of-day and traffic indicators) and predict the latitude/longitude of the next position. The centralized dataset is partitioned across three silos, each representing a subset of the network (e.g., geographic regions), and within each silo, devices are annotated with a tier label (Low, Mid, High).

To enable federated training, trajectories are pre-processed into fixed-length sequences and targets, stored as normalized coordinates using z-score statistics (mean and standard deviation of latitude and longitude). These statistics are shared across all experiments so that evaluation metrics can be computed in physical units (degrees and meters) in a comparable way across tiers and scenarios.

Trajectories processing

For this study, we consider a 14-day window from 22 July to 4 August 2024 and start from anonymized mobility traces of roughly 80,000 native MNO subscribers in a large metropolitan area. Only devices that are active over the monitored cell sites at least 80% of the time window and whose TAC corresponds to a smartphone are retained, keeping about 89% of the original sample and ensuring that trajectories correspond to handset-based mobility rather than fixed equipment. From the underlying signalling probes (handover and serving-cell updates), each anonymized user trajectory is represented as a time-ordered sequence of radio cells, as illustrated in Figure 8 (left), which shows the dense probe activity over the urban network.

Figure 8: (Left) High-level overview of measurements. (Right) Overview of the conversion from BS to grid.

To obtain a uniform and privacy-preserving spatial representation, we overlay the city with a regular grid of cells and map each base-station location to its corresponding grid cell, as shown in Figure 8 (right). A raw sequence of base stations such as $[B_1, B_{51}, B_{52}, B_9]$ thus becomes a shorter grid-cell trajectory $[G_1, G_5, G_9]$ when multiple base stations fall into the same cell. We then keep only users with at least 10 active days and 120 total records and drop device models with fewer than 20 users. This grid-based preprocessing reduces positioning noise, mitigates artefacts from vertical and dense horizontal handovers, and strengthens privacy by aggregating mobility over larger areas before trajectories are used in the tier-aware FL pipeline.

To illustrate how trajectory diversity manifests after this processing, Figure 9 shows two representative test-device trajectories on the grid. User A (orange) visits many cells over a wider area and exhibits higher entropy and radius of gyration (RoG), while User B (blue) moves within a much more confined region, resulting in lower entropy and RoG. These examples visually support our use of entropy and RoG as compact descriptors of mobility diversity across device tiers.

Figure 9: Trajectories from two test devices with differences in length and diversity, reflected on mobility statistics. User A(orange) - Entropy: 4.76, RoG: 0.12; User B (blue) - Entropy: 1.68, RoG: 0.01.

Tier-aware cross-silo configurations

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Following the taxonomy introduced, we consider multiple cross-silo tier configurations with three clients, which reflect realistic deployment choices and stress the FL system under different heterogeneity patterns. Examples include:

- Representative diversity (exp. 1): Silos inherit the natural tier distribution from the network, which is typically imbalanced (e.g., 22.1% of low-tier data, 29.4% of mid-tier, and 48,5% of high-tier for each client)
- Egalitarian diversity (exp. 2): Silos are constructed so that each tier represents an equal share (e.g., approximately 33% across tiers for each client), within each silo, decoupling tier imbalance from geographical or silo-level effects.
- Non-overlapping diversity (exp. 3 – exp. 5): Each silo is homogeneous (only one tier per client), which favors learning tier-specific mobility patterns but increases cross-silo heterogeneity. In this family of experiments, not every round necessarily involves all clients; selective participation is allowed to reflect system constraints (for example, stragglers, availability) and to analyse learning dynamics when only a subset of homogeneous silos contributes.

These configurations are performed using the most common FL strategy, FedAvg.

Model architecture and training setup

On each client, we train a sequence model for next-location prediction. In the current implementation, the default architecture is a recurrent neural network (RNN) or LSTM with:

- Input features encoding past locations and contextual variables.
- A hidden state capturing user mobility dynamics over the recent history.
- A regression head predicting the next latitude and longitude in normalized space.

The model is initialized centrally and distributed to all clients at the beginning of each FL experiment. Training proceeds over a fixed number of federated rounds. In each round, selected clients perform several local epochs of SGD on their local trajectories and then send model weights back to the server for aggregation. FedAvg computes a weighted average of local models.

All experiments share a common hyperparameter template (learning rate, batch size, number of local epochs, etc.) and differ only in:

- The tier configuration across silos.
- The training split is used for each scenario.

Centralized, tier-aware evaluation pipeline

To ensure consistent and comparable metrics across experiments, evaluation is performed centrally on a fixed held-out test set that mirrors the tier distribution of the deployed system. After each federated round, the global model is evaluated on this test set without further

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local training. For each sample, predictions are denormalized back to latitude/longitude using the global mean and standard deviation, and the following metric is computed:

- RMSE in meters, computed from the denormalized coordinates to quantify spatial error in physical units.

Experiments and Results

We evaluate all tier-aware cross-silo configurations introduced above using the centralized, tier-aware evaluation pipeline. For each experiment, we track per-tier RMSE in meters (computed from denormalized latitude/longitude via haversine distance) across FL rounds and summarize the final performance using fairness plots that compare Low, Mid, and High tiers side by side. The boxplot in Figure 10 reports the final RMSE in meters for all experiments, with the x-axis indicating the training-tier configuration (train-tiers) and the coloured boxes showing the error for each evaluation tier, enabling a direct visual comparison across all setups.

RMSE in meters is computed from denormalized latitude/longitude predictions using the haversine distance between predicted and true locations, providing a spatial error measure in physical units. Exp 1 corresponds to the representative diversity setting (22.1% Low-tier, 29.4% Mid-tier, 48.5% High-tier data per client), Exp 2 to the egalitarian diversity setting

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(33% of each tier per client), and Exps 3–5 to non-diversity settings where each client has only data from one tier (Exp 3: Low, Mid, High; Exp 4: Mid, High; Exp 5: High only).

Overall performance per tier and training set

Figure 10: Per-tier root mean squared error (RMSE) in meters for different training-tier cross-silo configurations.

In the **representative diversity** configuration (Exp. 1 in Figure 10), where each silo mirrors the natural tier imbalance of the network, the global model converges reliably and achieves strong overall accuracy. High- and Mid-tier users obtain low RMSE, while Low-tier users lag slightly behind but still benefit from being jointly trained with richer trajectories from higher tiers. This setting closely reflects a realistic deployment and shows how standard FedAvg behaves when the cross-silo tier distribution simply follows the live network.

In the **egalitarian diversity** configuration (Exp. 2 in Figure 10), where every silo is artificially balanced (approximately 33% of each tier per client), per-tier performance becomes more homogeneous. The gaps between High, Mid, and Low tiers shrink in RMSE, and the fairness plots show tighter, more overlapping curves across tiers. However, this comes with a modest loss in absolute performance for High-tier users compared to Exp. 1, since high-quality trajectories are “diluted” to enforce balance. Overall, Exp. 2 illustrates the trade-off between peak accuracy and cross-tier fairness when operators can engineer more balanced silo compositions.

The **non-overlapping diversity** configurations (Exps. 3–5 in Figure 10) expose more extreme scenarios where each silo contains only one tier. In Exp. 3 (three single-tier silos:

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Low, Mid, High), the model still sees the full tier spectrum, but only within separate silos. High-tier users enjoy very low RMSE, and Mid-tier users remain competitive, but Low-tier users do not improve as much as in the mixed-tier settings of Exps. 1–2, reflecting the fact that their trajectories are no longer “helped” by being co-located with richer data in the same silo. In Exp. 4, where only Mid- and High-tier silos participate, the model delivers good performance for Mid and High users but clearly underperforms for Low-tier evaluation, since the model never observes Low-tier trajectories during training and must extrapolate downward. Finally, Exp. 5, which trains exclusively on High-tier data, yields the lowest RMSE for High-tier users but degrades performance for Mid- and especially Low-tier users: the model overfits to the cleaner, denser mobility patterns of high-end devices and struggles to generalize to noisier or more sparsely sampled trajectories.

Taken together, Figure 10 shows that there is no single “best” configuration for all tiers. High-tier-only training (Exp. 5) is optimal if the objective is to minimize error for premium devices, but it does so at the expense of Mid- and Low-tier performance. Mixed-tier configurations that preserve all tiers in training (Exps. 1–3) yield more balanced behaviour: they slightly sacrifice the very best High-tier RMSE but significantly improve accuracy and robustness for Mid- and Low-tier users. This highlights a key design choice for telco operators: whether to optimize purely for top-tier devices or to accept a small loss in High-tier accuracy in exchange for fairer, more reliable performance across the entire device population

Conclusions

This work introduces a tier-aware Federated Learning framework for next-location prediction over JCAS-enhanced mobility data, explicitly modelling the heterogeneity between Low-, Mid-, and High-tier devices. Across a spectrum of tier-aware cross-silo configurations, the results show that while High-only training can minimize error for High-tier users, mixed-tier training – where all tiers are represented and High-tier trajectories are included – yields models that generalize better across the entire device population and substantially improve performance for constrained Low- and Mid-tier users compared to single-tier training. At the same time, configurations with balanced tier composition across silos lead to more homogeneous per-tier performance, improving fairness with only a modest loss in peak accuracy for top-tier devices.

From a telecom perspective, these findings are highly relevant: they demonstrate that FL can exploit existing tier diversity in operational networks to build more accurate and fair mobility-aware services (such as traffic and handover prediction) while respecting data locality and privacy constraints. The proposed tier-aware evaluation methodology and empirical analysis align with the broader objectives of Task 5.2, providing concrete evidence that federated, JCAS-enabled models can support more efficient and equitable network

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management across heterogeneous devices. Future work will combine this tier-aware setting with the personalized FL and PSI-based client selection mechanisms presented in Section 4.3.1 to further enhance convergence, robustness, and fairness in real deployments.

4.4 CRYPTOGRAPHIC INTEGRATION (DP, HE, DID LIBRARY)

4.4.1 TRUST AND IDENTITY LAYER FOR FEDERATED LEARNING

In Federated Learning (FL), a collection of distributed clients collaboratively trains a global model without sharing their raw data. While this paradigm preserves privacy, it introduces new challenges of trust, authentication, and verifiable participation. The server must ensure that each client is genuine, uncompromised, and authorized to contribute, while clients must trust that the orchestration infrastructure protects their contributions. Traditional, centralized authentication and Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) approaches cannot easily scale to heterogeneous and cross-organizational federations, nor can they offer decentralized assurance once models and participants span administrative boundaries.

To address these limitations, we introduce an Identity Layer that establishes cryptographic and procedural guarantees throughout the FL lifecycle, from onboarding and key provisioning to continuous verification during training and model aggregation. The layer is designed around the principles of Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) and integrates mechanisms for confidential computing, remote attestation, and zero-knowledge-based authorization. This combination enables verifiable yet privacy-preserving interactions between participants, ensuring both regulatory compliance (e.g., GDPR, EU AI Act) and operational resilience.

Conceptually, the builds directly upon the ledger-anchored SSI architecture defined in D2.4 Blockchain Toolkit, which replaced centralized identity directories with a decentralized, W3C-compliant identity fabric based on Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs). Deliverable 2.4 described how DIDs, VCs, and anonymous credentials can serve as the trust substrate for 6G-scale data spaces. Deliverable 4.4 extends this foundation to Federated Learning environments, specifying how identities, attestations, and access policies interact with federated orchestrators and confidential containers.

4.4.1.1 SELF-SOVEREIGN IDENTITY LAYER

The Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) layer constitutes the cryptographic trust foundation and extends the ledger-anchored identity model described in Deliverable 2.4 Blockchain Toolkit. It is adapted for dynamic FL environments, where clients, orchestrators, and data owners continuously join, contribute, and leave federations. SSI enables participants to generate and

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manage their own cryptographic identities (DIDs) without relying on central certificate authorities. Each DID is unique, and bound to a cryptographic key pair, ensuring verifiability through public–private key operations. DIDs resolve to DID Documents, expressed in JSON-LD, which describe verification methods, authentication mechanisms, and service endpoints.

The SSI layer also incorporates VCs, digitally signed attestations issued by trusted entities (issuers) to participants (holders). VCs encapsulate claims such as the participant’s role (e.g., Federated Learning Client), organizational affiliation, or hardware attestation status, which can be verified by any third party (verifier) through standard cryptographic proofs. This issuer–holder–verifier triad enables interoperable and trustworthy identity establishment among previously unacquainted participants.

In advanced deployments, the SSI layer further supports Anonymous Credentials (ACs) and Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs). These mechanisms allow participants to prove attributes, such as authorization level or TEE verification, without disclosing underlying identifiers or personal data. For example, a client can prove that it operates inside an attested enclave or belongs to a specific consortium without revealing its DID or organizational identity, ensuring compliance with GDPR principles such as data minimization and purpose limitation.

Integration of the SSI layer with Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) for storing private keys and credentials adds an additional layer of security and can prevent key extraction. This guarantees that cryptographic material never leaves the secure boundary of the participant’s device, while still allowing DID resolution and VC verification through the distributed ledger.

Beyond the cryptographic layer, SSI introduces a policy-driven governance model supporting hierarchical or federated trust anchors. Each organization in the federation may operate its own DID issuer, while cross-certification and credential chaining enable interoperability across domains. By embedding the SSI layer within the FL orchestration infrastructure, identity verification, credential issuance, and access control become autonomous and event-driven - triggered during onboarding, training rounds, or model aggregation.

4.4.1.2 ONBOARDING AND CONTINUOUS TRUST ASSURANCE WORKFLOW

To operate trust in FL systems, we define a structured onboarding and continuous assurance workflow consisting of the following steps:

Step 0 - DID Creation and Registration

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Each new participant (e.g., FL client or data provider) generates a DID locally, using a secure key pair managed within its wallet. The public portion of the DID, together with its metadata (verification methods, endpoints), is optionally anchored on a distributed ledger, ensuring immutability and global resolvability. This registry acts as the initial trust anchor, enabling other participants to verify the authenticity of the entity before data or model exchange begins.

Step 1 – VC Issuance and Role Binding

After registration, a trusted issuer (such as the FL orchestrator, consortium authority, or attestation service) issues a VC that certifies the participant’s role and permissions. The VC links the participant’s DID to its operational context (e.g., “Authorized FL Client – Tier 1 Data Owner”) and includes cryptographic proofs anchored to the ledger. These credentials are referenced by their DID and can be verified without requiring any central database, enabling decentralized access control and auditability.

Step 2 - Remote Attestation: Binding TEE Evidence to Identity

To ensure runtime integrity, each node equipped with a TEE performs a remote attestation. The attestation evidence, comprising a signed hardware report, is bound to the node’s DID, forming a verifiable link between digital identity and physical hardware trust. This evidence can be encapsulated as a VC or attached as signed metadata retrievable through DID resolution. The combination of DIDs, VCs, and TEEs ensures that only authenticated and uncompromised devices contribute to model updates.

Step 3 - Zero-Knowledge Access Token for Federated Rounds

Before participating in each federated training round, clients generate a ZKP-based access token, demonstrating possession of valid credentials and attested execution environments without revealing underlying secrets. The FL coordinator validates these proofs before aggregating model updates, ensuring privacy-preserving admission control. This approach minimizes leakage of sensitive information while maintaining cryptographic assurance that all contributors are legitimate.

Step 4 - Revocation, Re-Attestation, and Continuous Trust Assurance

The system continuously enforces trust integrity by monitoring for credential revocations and policy changes. Verifiable Credentials can be revoked in case of detected misbehaviour, outdated policies, or security breaches. Additionally, nodes are periodically required to re-attest to their hardware integrity and software compliance, ensuring continuous adherence to security baselines. Revocation lists and attestation registries are distributed across the

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federation, allowing coordinators to validate client eligibility dynamically before each participation cycle.

This structured workflow strengthens the trust fabric of FL environments while preserving decentralization and data privacy.

4.4.2 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DECENTRALIZED IDENTITY AND SECURE COMMUNICATION LAYER

The conceptual model outlined in the previous section specifies the trust, identity, and verification requirements for FL environments. This subsection focuses on the operational subset that has been implemented, namely decentralized identifier provisioning, authentication, secure-channel establishment, and encrypted metadata exchange, which is also integrated into UC3 and described in Deliverable 5.2. The implementation provides concrete mechanisms, protocols, and API endpoints that can be consumed directly by FL orchestrators, clients, and auxiliary pilot services.

The implemented identity and secure communication layer are exposed through a set of REST API endpoints provided by the NestJS backend. These endpoints support the full operational lifecycle of decentralized identity within the system, including user onboarding, authentication, DID-based connection establishment, and encrypted message exchange. Collectively, these interfaces form a programmable integration layer that enables FL orchestrators and client components to authenticate participants, establish secure channels, and exchange confidential metadata. Documentation of the reference implementation, including the exposed API endpoints, is accessible at [37].

Identity Provisioning and DID Generation: The system implements decentralized identity provisioning as part of its onboarding workflow. When a new participant registers through the /auth/register endpoint, the system generates a decentralized identifier (DID) together with an associated asymmetric keypair, which is securely stored within the participant's local agent. A corresponding DID Document is created to specify the verification methods and service endpoints in compliance with decentralized identity standards. The registration interface returns the DID, public verification key, and the relevant communication endpoint to the registering entity, making DID creation fully operationalized and accessible to FL orchestrators, clients, and auxiliary services. By shifting identity creation and key custody to the edge of the FL network, the system eliminates dependence on central certificate authorities and enables cryptographically verifiable, self-managed identities for all participating components.

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Authentication and Access Control: Authentication is performed through the `/auth/sign-in` endpoint, which issues short-lived access tokens that enable secure and controlled interaction with the system's protected interfaces. These tokens provide the enforcement layer required for identity-gated operations such as message exchange and secure-channel establishment. By combining decentralized key management with conventional web-security constructs (JWT-based authentication), the implementation provides a practical bridge between SSI-based identity and FL orchestration workflows.

To support confidential communication between distributed components, the system provides a secure messaging workflow based on pairwise, DID-authenticated channels. Connection establishment is performed through a two-step process in which an initiating entity generates a connection invitation (`/connections/establish`), and the counterparty accepts it (`/connections/accept`). Once a pairwise channel is formed, entities can exchange encrypted messages through the `/messages` endpoint.

All cryptographic operations, including message encryption and decryption, take place exclusively within the local agents of the communicating parties, ensuring full end-to-end confidentiality. The backend infrastructure never accesses or processes plaintext content. Message retrieval on the recipient side occurs via `/messages/{id}/unpack`, which returns only the decrypted payload to the authenticated entity.

In alignment with data-minimization principles, the system does not persist any plain-text messages. The backend stores only encrypted envelopes together with minimal routing metadata such as timestamps, sender and recipient identifiers, and connection references. All private keys remain strictly confined to local agents, preventing the orchestrator or any intermediary component from inspecting sensitive communication content. This architecture satisfies the confidentiality requirements of federated learning, where both model updates and coordination metadata must remain inaccessible to coordinating servers.

Integration Hooks for Federated Learning: The identity and communication layer provides all necessary building blocks for authenticated and verifiable participation. The system exposes mechanisms for DID-based participant onboarding, secure client-orchestrator communication, and confidential message routing across distributed nodes. These capabilities allow FL orchestrators to verify participant identity, enforce per-round authorization policies, and maintain a trusted substrate for coordination without requiring any exposure of sensitive model updates or metadata.

4.5 BLOCKCHAIN-ENABLED AGGREGATION (SMART CONTRACTS, REPUTATION SYSTEMS, IPFS)

Blockchain-enabled aggregation provides a foundational trust layer for FL by decentralizing the verification and storage of model updates, preventing single points of failure, and enabling transparent provenance across multiple administrative domains. In Task 4.4, blockchain integration strengthens the resilience of the FL process against poisoning attacks, malicious client behaviour, and aggregator compromise. This design is directly informed by our recent research at UCD, particularly the defence architecture proposed in “Decentralized Defense: Leveraging Blockchain Against Poisoning Attacks in Federated Learning Systems” [38], which demonstrates how blockchain, IPFS, and decentralized oracle networks can collectively enhance the security and accountability of FL workflows.

4.5.1 DECENTRALIZING AGGREGATION TO ELIMINATE THE SINGLE POINT OF FAILURE

Traditional Federated Learning architectures rely on a central aggregator that collects local model updates and produces the global model. While straightforward, this approach introduces a critical vulnerability: if the central aggregator is compromised or behaves maliciously, it can manipulate global parameters, suppress legitimate contributions, introduce poisoned updates, or bias the final model outcome. Blockchain-based aggregation mitigates this risk by redistributing trust across a decentralized ledger and computing network rather than relying on a single authority. This transition ensures that model updates are both verifiable and tamper-evident, significantly strengthening the overall security of the FL workflow.

In this work, two blockchain-assisted FL models illustrate how aggregation can be secured through decentralization: the Centralized Aggregated BCFL (CA-BCFL) illustrated in Figure 11 and the Fully Decentralized BCFL (FD-BCFL) illustrated in Figure 12. In CA-BCFL, a central aggregator is still responsible for producing the global model; however, integrity is enforced through blockchain-based registration of Content Identifiers (CIDs) for all local updates. Each client uploads its model to IPFS, and only the CID is stored on-chain, producing a transparent and immutable audit trail of participation and ensuring that the aggregator cannot discard or alter updates without detection.

Figure 11: Workflow of the Centralized aggregation BCFL system

In contrast, FD-BCFL eliminates the central aggregator altogether. Here, aggregation is performed by a decentralized oracle network—such as Chain-link nodes—that retrieve local updates from IPFS, execute malicious-mitigation and robust aggregation computations off-chain, and reach consensus on the updated global model. This consensus result is then recorded on the blockchain, creating a tamper-resistant provenance trail. By removing centralized control and distributing computation across independent validators, FD-BCFL provides a stronger guarantee that no single party can manipulate the training process.

Together, these two models demonstrate how blockchain ensures that every training iteration is verifiable, auditable, and protected against manipulation, whether aggregation remains centralized (CA-BCFL) or becomes fully decentralized (FD-BCFL).

Figure 12: Workflow of the Fully decentralized BCFL system

4.5.2 SMART CONTRACTS FOR COORDINATION AND MODEL PROVENANCE

Smart contracts act as the coordination logic for blockchain-enabled federated learning. They manage the submission of model update references, maintain the version history of global models, and define the policies governing aggregation rounds. When clients finish their local training, they upload their model to IPFS and register the corresponding CID in the smart contract. The contract then triggers validation or aggregation procedures depending on the design (CA-BCFL or FD-BCFL).

The smart contract's interaction with the Chain-link Decentralized Oracle Network (DON), as shown in Figure 13, enables secure off-chain computation. Once a compute request is initiated, oracle nodes retrieve the model updates from IPFS, perform malicious-mitigation analysis or aggregation, and submit their consensus result back to the contract. This ensures that the blockchain maintains an authoritative and tamper-evident record of validated model updates without performing expensive computations on-chain. Smart contracts, therefore, serve as both the governance mechanism and the audit layer for the entire FL lifecycle.

Figure 13: Architecture of the Off-chain computation process

4.5.3 IPFS AS SCALABLE OFF-CHAIN STORAGE FOR MODEL ARTIFACTS

Blockchain alone cannot store the large parameter sets associated with modern machine learning models. To address this limitation, both CA-BCFL and FD-BCFL employ IPFS (Interplanetary File System) as the decentralized storage mechanism for model files. Instead of storing raw updates on-chain, clients upload their models to IPFS, which assigns each file a cryptographic CID. The CID uniquely identifies the content and can be used to retrieve the file from any IPFS node.

This architecture ensures scalability while retaining strong security guarantees. Since the CID is a cryptographic hash of the model file, any modification to the file immediately produces a different hash, allowing smart contracts or oracle nodes to detect tampering. IPFS, therefore, complements blockchain by providing secure, distributed, and tamper-evident storage that supports large FL model artifacts without imposing on-chain cost burdens.

4.5.4 OFF-CHAIN MALICIOUS-MITIGATION USING DECENTRALIZED ORACLE NETWORKS

One of the most innovative components described in the referenced paper is the use of decentralized oracle networks to perform malicious-mitigation computations off-chain. Tasks such as robust aggregation, anomaly detection, or gradient sanitization are computationally expensive and cannot be executed inside blockchain smart contracts. By leveraging Chain-link DON, the system delegates these tasks to a decentralized set of computation nodes that independently retrieve model updates from IPFS, apply defence algorithms, and reach consensus on the final output.

This workflow, illustrated in Figure 13, ensures that no single oracle node can manipulate the aggregation result. Each node performs the computation independently, and the final result is accepted only if a consensus across nodes is reached. The validated model is then returned to the smart contract, which records the CID of the validated global model on-chain.

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This architecture preserves the decentralization of trust while maintaining efficiency and scalability.

4.5.5 REPUTATION, TRACEABILITY, AND ATTACK DETECTION

Blockchain naturally provides a transparent and immutable log of all local and global model updates, enabling fine-grained provenance tracking. Each training round produces a record that includes the CIDs of all client updates, the identifier of the aggregated model, and, in the case of FD-BCFL, the validated malicious suppression result. Over time, this builds a complete history of participation and behaviour, making it possible to identify clients that consistently submit anomalous updates or participate in poisoning attempts.

The reported results in our work demonstrate that both CA-BCFL and FD-BCFL retain high model accuracy even when 20–60% of participating clients are malicious. The blockchain-assisted architectures also exhibit significantly lower gas costs compared to full on-chain FL, highlighting their practicality for real-world deployments. This reputation and traceability layer provides a foundation for client scoring, exclusion policies, and incentive mechanisms that further reinforce trust in federated learning.

In summary, Blockchain-enabled aggregation in Task 4.4 introduces a secure, transparent, and tamper-resistant mechanism for federated learning. By delegating model storage to IPFS, coordinating interactions through smart contracts, and leveraging decentralized oracle networks for off-chain validation, the architecture removes the traditional single point of failure and strengthens resilience against poisoning and manipulation. The integration of blockchain creates an auditable provenance trail that supports accountability, reputation management, and compliance. Together, these components form a robust aggregation framework that aligns directly with the privacy-preserving, trustworthy, and auditable AI objectives of the CONFIDENTIAL-6G project.

4.5.6 EVALUATION INSIGHTS FROM BLOCKCHAIN-ASSISTED AGGREGATION

Both CA-BCFL and FD-BCFL successfully preserve the same robustness and accuracy as the underlying defence algorithms under moderate poisoning levels. As shown in Figure 14, the accuracy curves of the BCFL models almost overlap with those of conventional FL, indicating that blockchain integration does not increase model-level robustness but ensures that accuracy is not degraded by decentralization.

Another key observation from the evaluation is the considerable reduction in blockchain transaction cost, illustrated in Table 3. Since both BCFL designs store model parameters in IPFS and record only the corresponding CIDs on-chain, the gas cost remains very low compared to fully on-chain approaches. This confirms that the hybrid blockchain–IPFS architecture is both scalable and economically viable.

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While FD-BCFL does not provide higher accuracy than CA-BCFL, it offers stronger system-level security by eliminating the single point of failure. As illustrated in Figure 12, decentralized oracle nodes independently execute and validate off-chain malicious-mitigation computations before committing the global model CID to the blockchain, ensuring tamper-proof traceability and resilience against aggregator compromise.

Overall, the experimental results demonstrate that blockchain-enabled aggregation is well-suited for Task 4.4, as it preserves the robustness of the underlying FL defence mechanisms while providing strong system-level security guarantees. The BCFL architecture delivers low operational cost through the hybrid blockchain-IPFS design and offers high auditability and traceability—capabilities that directly support the security, transparency, and reliability objectives of the CONFIDENTIAL-6G federated learning framework.

Figure 14: Test Accuracy of the source class under Label-flipping attack

Table 3: The average transaction fee for the CA-BCFL

System Models	Transaction Fee (ETH)			
	Gas for initiating requests		Callback gas	
	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
CA-BCFL	1.60^{-9}	0.00156	$0.76e^{-9}$	0.00068
FD-BCFL	$1.73e^{-9}$	0.00164	$0.76e^{-9}$	0.00070

5 INTEGRATION ASPECTS

5.1 INTEGRATION IN WP5 USE CASES

5.1.1 INTEGRATION IN USE CASE 1: PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE FOR AIRLINE CONSORTIUM

In Use Case 1, federated learning is used to help organisations in the aviation domain work together on predictive maintenance without sharing their raw data. Airlines and manufacturers all collect useful information about engines and aircraft systems, but this data is sensitive, private, and often too large to move. Because of this, traditional approaches—where all data must be gathered into one place—are not possible.

Enhancing the Nokia Data Marketplace with federated learning organisations can train part of a shared AI model locally on its own systems. Only the model updates—not the data itself—are shared back. This allows involved stakeholders to benefit from a richer, combined model without exposing confidential information.

The federated learning process is orchestrated through the Flower framework, which manages how updates are exchanged between participants. The model is packaged in confidential containers and executed on edge servers located near airports or aircraft.

To ensure privacy at every step, the approach also strives to combine federated learning with Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) to enable computations on encrypted data, Secure Multiparty Computation to ensure model updates remain private, Blockchain to record actions such as key creation, training steps, access rights, so that the process is transparent and trustworthy and finally Identity and access management to ensure only approved parties can participate in training.

The initial experiments show that federated learning works quite well in the scope of the use case and can be practical and effective for aviation predictive maintenance. Apart from the Nokia Data Marketplace this work is also relevant for WINGS commercial products that address fleet operations in a privacy-preserving way.

Overall, this use case demonstrates how federated learning combined with encrypted computation, blockchain audit logging, secure containers and edge execution can allow different organisations to collaborate on AI safely and efficiently, something that was previously very difficult in the aviation sector.

5.1.2 INTEGRATION IN USE CASE 3: INTELLIGENT-CONNECTED VEHICLE, FL/ML AND VEHICLE TO INFRASTRUCTURE COMMUNICATION

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Use case 3 – Intelligent Connected Vehicle, FL/ML and Vehicle to Infrastructure Communication integrates various technologies presented in this document. Between others, it leverages Federated Learning algorithms introduced in Section 4.3.

In particular, the algorithm to foster convergence under non-IID scenarios, introduced in Section 4.3.1, is used to mitigate the data heterogeneity problem present in telco data when federated sensors (base stations) are utilized. This occurs for both the traffic congestion and the handover prediction tasks.

Use case 3 also tries to showcase how federated learning can support the derivation of insights on driving behaviour and assessing road infrastructure conditions. The driving behaviour work combines information from a vehicle's onboard diagnostics (OBD) sensors with data from smartphone sensors to understand how drivers behave on the road. These two data sources complement each other: OBD data reflects the performance of the vehicle itself, while smartphone sensors capture motion and orientation linked to the driver's actions. Analysis shows that features such as average speed, instantaneous speed, fuel consumption, and speed variation are strong indicators of whether someone drives calmly or aggressively. When trained centrally, the models achieve very high accuracy. In a federated learning setup—where data stays on each device, and only model updates are shared—the accuracy remains strong, with only a small reduction. This demonstrates that it is possible to draw reliable conclusions about driving behaviour while keeping personal mobility data private and local. The road infrastructure assessment focuses on detecting damage from video streams captured by vehicles. Incoming frames are first enhanced using contrast-improvement techniques, which make cracks and irregularities more visible. A deep learning model then identifies damage within each frame, classifying its type and extracting additional metadata such as size and texture. Testing on a large number of annotated images shows that the model performs reliably, achieving high precision and strong overall accuracy. Importantly, it generalises well across different platforms: whether the data comes from a ground vehicle or a drone, the model is able to identify cracks and potholes consistently, despite changes in perspective or lighting. In the federated learning setting, for each vehicle, there is local training on the images it collects, and it sends only the updated model weights back to a central coordinator. This avoids the need to transmit large volumes of video data and ensures that potentially sensitive location-based imagery stays on the device. Although federated training leads to a drop in performance, it still performs well and provides important privacy benefits.

Both the driving behaviour and road infrastructure assessment are being integrated into commercial products (wi.supply [39] and wi.move [40]), enabling practical use in fleet management and road maintenance operations.

More details are provided in D5.2.

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable has specified, designed, and partially validated a federated AI/ML framework tailored to the confidentiality, security, and trust requirements of 6G-era networks and data spaces. Building on the confidential orchestration substrate of Task 4.3 and the cryptographic enablers of WP2 and WP3, Task 4.4 has defined how federated learning can operate end-to-end across a heterogeneous cloud-edge continuum while keeping data local, protecting model updates, and enabling verifiable, policy-driven collaboration among mutually distrusting parties.

A first contribution is the systematic analysis of **requirements and threat models** for Federated AI/ML in 6G. The deliverable has identified key functional needs (scalable orchestration, heterogeneity handling, support for edge and IoT devices), security and privacy guarantees (confidentiality of data and updates, integrity of training and infrastructure, and fairness across non-IID populations), as well as ORAN-specific constraints and attacker models involving honest-but-curious entities, malicious clients, compromised aggregators, and cross-domain adversaries. These requirements directly inform the design choices of the architecture and provide a reusable checklist for subsequent WP4 and WP5 activities.

On top of this, the deliverable has introduced a **modular federated learning architecture** that cleanly separates policy and monitoring, security and aggregation, federated coordination, and confidential execution. The Operator Monitoring & Policy Interface gives operators visibility and control over FL workflows; the Security, Validation, and Aggregation layer combines client validation, platform attestation, and secure aggregation; the Federation & Orchestration layer manages client selection, resource- and energy-aware scheduling, and round coordination; and the Infrastructure layer provides TEE- and container-based confidential runtimes enriched with privacy-preserving mechanisms such as DP, HE, and SMPC. This decomposition ensures that FL tasks can be deployed close to data sources while preserving end-to-end confidentiality, integrity, and auditability.

A second major contribution is the **integration of advanced cryptographic and trust mechanisms** into the FL pipeline. The work shows how Differential Privacy, Homomorphic Encryption, Secure Multi-Party Computation, threshold cryptography, and post-quantum primitives can be combined with confidential computing platforms (SEV-SNP, TDX, CCA, etc.) to protect data in use, in transit, and at rest. In parallel, a Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) layer based on Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), Verifiable Credentials (VCs), and Zero-Knowledge Proofs provides a decentralized identity and authorization fabric for FL participants, tightly coupled with remote attestation and secure communication channels. This identity and trust layer is implemented through DID-aware APIs and secure messaging workflows that can be directly consumed by orchestrators and pilot services and is already being integrated in WP5 UC3.

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The deliverable also advances the state of the art in **blockchain-enabled aggregation for FL**. By leveraging distributed ledgers, IPFS, and decentralized oracle networks, Task 4.4 replaces the classical single trusted aggregator with blockchain-assisted designs that offer tamper-evident provenance and Byzantine-resilient aggregation. The proposed CA-BCFL and FD-BCFL schemes demonstrate how model artefacts can be stored off-chain, referenced by immutable content identifiers, and processed by oracle nodes that collaboratively validate and aggregate local updates before committing a new global model state on-chain. Experimental evidence confirms that these designs preserve the robustness of the underlying defences while significantly reducing on-chain costs and eliminating single points of failure, aligning directly with the transparency and auditability goals of CONFIDENTIAL6G.

From an algorithmic perspective, Task 4.4 contributes two complementary research lines for **robust and fair FL under heterogeneity**. The PSI-PFL framework introduces the Population Stability Index as both a metric for quantifying label skew and a client-selection criterion, achieving up to 10% relative accuracy gains over state-of-the-art baselines while improving client-level fairness in non-IID scenarios. In parallel, the tier-aware FL framework for JCAS-enhanced mobility data explicitly models device-tier heterogeneity (Low/Mid/High) and studies how cross-silo tier configurations impact accuracy and fairness for next-location prediction. Results show that mixed-tier FL configurations, where all tiers participate, yield models that generalize better across the entire device population, providing concrete design guidance for telecom operators deploying FL-based mobility services.

Finally, the deliverable has outlined how the proposed Federated AI/ML framework **integrates into WP5 use cases**, notably predictive maintenance for airline consortia (Use Case 1) and intelligent connected vehicles with V2I communication (Use Case 3). In these scenarios, the FL architecture, confidential containers, cryptographic enablers, and blockchain-based audit trails are instantiated to enable cross-organizational AI collaboration without raw data sharing, to cope with non-IID telco data, and to prepare for commercial exploitation in products such as wi.supply and wi.move. This validates that the solutions developed in Task 4.4 are not only theoretically sound but also practically relevant for 6G-class verticals. In summary, this deliverable establishes the Federated AI/ML system as the point where confidential orchestration, advanced cryptography, decentralized trust, and robust learning algorithms converge. It provides WP4 and WP5 with a coherent architecture, concrete implementations, and validated methods for secure, privacy-preserving, and fair federated intelligence in 6G environments, laying a solid foundation for subsequent integration, experimentation, and exploitation within CONFIDENTIAL6G.

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